

Based on field cage trials, seven spider species were found to be efficient predators: *Lucosa* sp., *Pholcys* sp., *Marpissa mandali* Tikader, *Tetragnatha* sp., *Linyphia* sp., *Oxyopes sakuntalae* Tikader, and *Argiope undulata* Thorell. Their feeding potential is being investigated. ■

Natural biological suppression agents of rice pests in the eastern plains of Colombia

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The ecology of paddy rice pests was investigated during three successive growing semesters in 1977-78 at the La Libertad experiment station, Villavicencio, Meta. Control measures were not necessary because each potential economic pest was suppressed by natural enemies.

Trichogramma sp. or *Telenomus* sp. parasitized >95% of the eggs of the sugarcane stem borer *Diatraea saccharalis* F. The larval parasitoid *Agathis stigmaterus* Cresson was active in the plots each season. Borer damage never exceeded 3%, the level along borders.

During each crop unidentified epizootics of entomopathogens suppressed populations of leafhopper, mainly *Hortensia similis* (Walker) and *Draeculacephala clypeata* Osborn, by 70 to 95% (field estimate). Those species never caused an economic level of damage. The defoliators *Spodoptera* spp. and *Panoquina* spp. were effectively suppressed by fungal epizootics of *Paecilomyces tenuipes* (Peck) Samson (identified by R. A. Humber, Boyce Thompson Institute, Ithaca, N.Y., USA). Estimates of successful field infection rates ranged from 95 to 99% during each crop, which apparently was sufficient to maintain the species at lower than economic levels. Various tachnids parasitized the Pentatomid species. The rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus oryzophilus* Kuschel (considered the Legion's major rice pest) was absent from the experimental plots.

No pest control measures were necessary because of the natural suppression complexes in the fields during the three rice crops.

Noe Arias, Practico, ICA, La Libertad, Villavicencio, collected *Diatraea* eggs and did most of the laboratory parasite counts. ■

Field efficacy of a fungus, a bacterium, and organic insecticides against rice pests

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The successful control of vegetable pests with low doses of organic insecticides and entomogenous organisms has encouraged the testing of such

combinations against rice insect pests.

A field trial was established to determine the performance of white halo fungus (*Cephalosporium lecanii* Zimm.), a bacterium (*Bacillus thuringiensis* var. *alesti* Berliner Dipel), and of the two with dichlorvos or phosalone.

Phosalone reduced rice borer incidence slightly. Neither the fungus nor the bacterium reduced incidence of whorl maggot, stem borer, or leaf folder.

Effect of combinations of insect pathogens and insecticides on the incidence of rice insect pests. Tamil Nadu, India.

Treatment	Damage ^a (%)			Yield (t/ha)
	Whorl maggot	Stem borer	Leaf roller	
Fungus (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml)	12.6 d	11.9 b	0.6 c	2.9
Fungus + phosalone (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml) (1.42 ml/liter)	11.6 c	13.3 c	0.3 ab	3.1
Fungus + dichlorvos (16 x 10 ⁴ spores/ml) (2 ml/liter)	10.9 b	11.7 b	0.4 bc	3.2
Dipel (5.5 g/liter)	11.6 c	11.3 b	0.5 bc	3.2
Dipel + phosalone (2.75 g/liter) (1.42 ml/liter)	13.1 d	11.6 b	1.4 e	3.2
Dipel + dichlorvos (2.75 g/liter) (2 ml/liter)	11.9 c	12.4 b	0.2 ab	2.9
Phosalone (2.85 ml/liter)	10.3 a	8.6 a	0.5 c	3.3
Dichlorvos (4 ml/liter)	11.7 c	9.6 a	0.1 a	3.4
Phosalone + dichlorvos (1.42 ml/liter) (2 ml/liter)	11.4 bc	11.6 b	0.2 ab	3.2
Untreated control	11.9 d	12.4 c	0.4 d	2.3
Significance	*	*	*	n.s.
CD at 5% level	0.5	1.2	0.25	

^a Mean values with the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

Ovicidal and larvicidal activity of some insecticides on leaf folder

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Four insecticides — methyl parathion, triazophos, methomyl, and carbofuran — at 0.04% concentration were tested on eggs and freshly hatched larvae of the leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*. Two-day-old eggs of leaf folder from the greenhouse culture were dipped in the prepared insecticidal solutions for

1 minute. The control was eggs dipped in water. Both treated and untreated eggs were placed in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and were observed daily. Three days after the treatment, the control eggs hatched. Most treated eggs did not hatch although embryonic development was completed (see table). Some eggs treated with methomyl hatched but the larvae were weak and died within minutes. In an earlier study ovicidal activity of carbofuran and triazophos against the